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The detection of generator bearing failures on wind turbines using machine learning based anomaly detection

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Abstract.

In this research an early warning methodological framework is developed that is able to detect premature failures due to excessive wear. The methodology follows the data-driven Normal Behavior Model (NBM) principle, in which one or more data-driven models are used to model the normal behavior of the wind turbine. Anomalous behaviour of the turbine is identified by analyzing the deviation between the observed and predicted normal behaviour. The framework consists of two pipelines, a statistics and machine learning based pipeline. The former is based on techniques like ARIMA, OLS and CUSUM. The latter makes use of techniques like Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, ... Each pipeline has its strengths and weaknesses, but by combining them in an intelligent way, a more capable detector is developed. The methodology is validated on 10-minute SCADA data from a real operational wind farm. The validation case focuses on generator (front/rear) bearing failures. The goal is to predict these failures well in advance (ideally at least a month) using the developed framework, which should allow for timely adjustments to the maintenance plan. The results show that the methodology is able to accomplish this reliably.

1. Introduction

The recent push towards renewable energy production has increased the investments in the wind turbine sector dramatically. In 2020 alone, over 90 gigawatts (GW) of new wind power production facilities were installed according to the Global Wind Report 2021. This brings the total installed energy production capacity to 743 GW, which is a growth of 14% compared to the year before [1]. To keep this inflow of money into the sector going, the profitability of the investments needs to be guaranteed. An important factor in this is the maintenance cost. Recent studies have shown that the operation and maintenance of wind turbines makes up 25-40% of the levelized cost of energy [2]. This means that keeping these costs under control is of paramount importance.

A major driver of these costs are premature failures due to excessive wear. These are caused, among other things, by high loads due to environmental conditions and aggressive control actions [3], [4], [5]. Therefore, predicting these types of failures would significantly reduce the operational cost of wind turbines, by avoiding unexpected downtime, and boost the profitability of the

investments. The research presented here is a contribution to condition monitoring of wind turbines using Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition (SCADA) data. More specifically, the focus lies on the identification of generator bearing failures.

The methodology presented in this paper is based on the Normal Behaviour Modelling (NBM) principle for modelling the behaviour of the wind turbine, and statistical analysis for the identification of anomalies in the difference between the observed and the predicted normal behaviour. The novelty of the method developed here lies in the combination of statistics and machine learning based pipelines. Each of these techniques have their strengths and weaknesses. The statistical ones require only a small amount of training data and computational power. However, they are less able to model complex non-linear relations. The machine learning techniques on the other hand require much more data and computational power, but are much more proficient in capturing complex non-linearities. The statistical models are useful as a first fast "scan" of the data, while the machine learning can be used for a more precise identification of anomalies. Furthermore, the statistics-based pipeline (S-pipeline) is turbine-based which means that it takes only information of a single turbine into account. The machine learning based pipeline (ML-pipeline) uses information of the whole fleet (fleet-based).

The SCADA data used to validate the methodology comes from a large operational wind farm. The observation period stretches over 10 years. Information on generator bearing failures has been made available by the wind turbine operator. For confidentiality reasons the validation case is based on only a subset of the data (10 wind turbines and 35 replacements).

2. Related work

Research into the detection of anomalies in SCADA data of wind turbines is currently a hot topic. This strong interest is driven by the fact that more and more sensor data from wind turbines has become available. Several different methodologies have been developed over time for the detection of anomalies. According to [6] a distinction can be made between model-based signal processing and data-driven methods. Alternatively, [7] divide SCADA data-based failure detection and condition monitoring systems into six groups: trending, clustering, NBM, damage modelling, alarm assessment and performance monitoring. In what follows a short overview is given of recent and/or important relevant work.

[8] use deep autoencoder (DAE) models as NBMs for the detection of anomalies and failures in wind turbines. The DAEs are trained on healthy or normal data and tested on the remaining data. The reconstruction error is used as a proxy for the deviation between the predicted normal values and the true observed values. An observation is considered an anomaly if the error surpasses an adaptive threshold that is based on Extreme Value Theory. They apply the methodology on several cases, a.o the identification of anomalies in the generator rear bearing temperature. [9] use neural networks as NBMs. The predictors of the models were selected using domain knowledge and data-driven feature selection techniques. For the analysis of the difference between the predicted normal and observed values they use a moving average. Their use case was the prediction of bearing faults. For this they used SCADA data with a resolution of 10 seconds. They were able to predict failures 1.5 hours in advance. [10] also rely on neural networks for the NBM. The deviations between the predicted normal and the true observed values are analyzed using the mahalanobis distance. The methodology is used to predict problems with gearbox bearings. As input they also use SCADA data. [11] combine SCADA data with a 5-minute resolution and status and fault data. For this they developed a three-layered methodology. The first level identifies status/faults. The second level predicts the severity of the failure and the third level predicts a specific error. They showed that their methodology is able to predict errors with a reasonable accuracy. [12] makes use of neural networks and Gaussian processes to create reference power curves for the wind turbines. As input SCADA data is used. Once the reference power curves are created, they investigate how well each power curve fits to the other turbines

of the fleet. A confusion matrix is created of the mean squared errors (MSE) of the predictions for each reference power curve on each wind turbine. The MSE values are subsequently used to identify anomalies.

[13] develop a condition monitoring system (CMS) that is based on vibration analysis. It contains four steps: angular resampling, identification of peaks, priority labeling and frequency tracking. They obtain a sensitivity of 97.62% and a specificity of 99.21%. In [14] an NBM is developed that is based on combining several machine learning models. The predictions of this combined model are compared to the true observed values. Their use case is the detection and quantification of power generation anomalies. A different approach is followed in [15]. In this paper a multi-target NBM is used, that is able to predict multiple target signals at the same time. This has the advantage that less single-target NBM models need to be developed and maintained, and the multi-target models have the tendency to outperform the single-target NBMs. SCADA data with a 10-minute resolution is used as input. [16] use Extreme Learning Machines for the prediction of failures in wind turbine generators and gearboxes. SCADA data with a 5-minute resolution is used as input. [17] combine convolution neural networks (CNN) and linear regression models. As input they use SCADA data with a 10-minute resolution. They also showed that transfer learning has potential for this kind of use cases by successfully transferring a model trained on one turbine to other turbines in the same fleet or other fleets. This has advantages when the amount of healthy data, which is a requirement for NBMs, is limited. Transfer learning is also used in [18]. [19] detect generator faults by combining an autoencoder with alarm logs of several fleets of wind turbines. The combination of these two sources leads to a drastic performance increase of the methodology. [20] use hierarchical clustering and pairwise similarity-based anomaly scoring to detect faulty turbines. For this they make use of fleet information, by looking for turbines of which the signature deviates from that of the fleet. Fleet information is also used in [21], where a fleet aggregate filters out factors that have a macro-level or fleet-wide effect, e.g. ambient temperature, wind conditions, ... Using this information together with statistical techniques (e.g. ARIMA, OLS, CUSUM), makes it possible to detect generator bearing failures with a high accuracy. Further information on the current state-of-the-art can be found in [22], [23].

The novelty of the methodology presented in this paper compared to the work discussed above lies in the exploitation of the strengths of statistical techniques and machine learning by combining them. The statistical methods can be used for a fast scan of the data while still obtaining good performance. The machine learning techniques can subsequently be used for more precise analysis. Furthermore, the framework combines turbine and fleet information. This means that more information is taken into account compared to the previously described techniques. Thanks to the statistical techniques, the framework is also more transparent. Furthermore, the focus of this research is on slow, long-term processes that stretch over many months. For these cases failure alerts should be raised at least a month (not days or hours) before the actual failure.

3. Methodology

In this paper a methodological framework is presented that is able to detect generator bearing failures (e.g. failures of the front and rear generator bearings). It is based on a data-driven NBM approach that makes use of historical data in batch format. This data is SCADA data with a resolution of 10 minutes. The framework consists of two pipelines. The first pipeline (the statistics based pipeline or S-pipeline) is meant to do a fast/crude scan of the data. It aggregates the data to day-level and makes use of statistical modelling (e.g. CUSUM). The second pipeline (the machine learning-based pipeline or ML-pipeline) is a slower (or more computationally intensive) but more precise scan. It aggregates data to hour-level and makes use of machine learning.

Figure 1. Schematic overview of the methodological framework with the two pipelines.

Table 1. Table containing overview of the target and the support variables.

Signal type	Signal name	Symbol
target 1	Generator front bearing temp.	T_{front}
target 2	Generator rear bearing temp.	T_{rear}
support 1	active power	P_{active}
support 2	nacelle temp.	$T_{nacelle}$
support 3	wind speed	S_{wind}
support 4	rotor speed	S_{rotor}

There are several reasons for using this two-pipeline approach. Firstly, traditional statistical models like CUSUM require much less training data than machine learning models. This makes it possible to detect anomalies with much less data. It also avoids the costly collection of a substantial training dataset. Moreover, the technique can also be used as a way to extract healthy training data from unverified data. Secondly, even though CUSUM can not model complex non-linear relations, it is still highly sensitive for slow-moving trends (e.g. changes in bearing temperatures due to wear). Thirdly, the machine learning based pipeline is useful to further refine the detections by the statistical model. This should allow for more precise failure alerts. Fourthly, the statistical modelling is more limited in the dimensionality of the input data it can properly handle. This restricts the S-pipeline to a single turbine perspective (turbine-based), which means it only takes into account information of one turbine at a time. On the other hand the ML-pipeline has, due to the inclusion of a feature selection step, not this restriction. This allows it to take the whole fleet into account (fleet-based). Combining these two perspectives allows the framework to use more information, which is beneficial for the accuracy of the detector. Fifthly, the framework gains transparency due to the S-pipeline. Figure 1 gives a schematic overview of the framework and its two-pipeline structure.

Before any data can be fed into the statistical and machine learning models, it needs to be preprocessed. This procedure contains several steps, a.o. standardisation of column names and units, removal of measurement errors, aggregation of the data to a specified level (e.g. hour for the ML-pipeline or day for the S-pipeline), and filtering out macro-level effects from the signals. This last step is done using the method described in [21]. The signals are decomposed in a common and an idiosyncratic component (Eq. 1). The common component captures effects that impact the whole fleet (macro-level), e.g. ambient temperature, wind speed, ..., and is calculated by normalizing the signals using their fleet counterpart. The idiosyncratic component captures the turbine specific elements. It is the latter component that will be used for the anomaly detection, because failures are turbine specific events.

The S-pipeline uses a modified version of the methodology developed in [21]. CUSUM, a technique from the Statistical Process Control (SPC) domain and developed in [24], is used to detect anomalies in the target signals (see table 1). It is sensitive for small and gradual

Figure 2. Schematic overview of the different steps in the S-pipeline.

$$y_{i,t} = f_t + \epsilon_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

$$\hat{\epsilon}_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^p \phi_{j,i} X_{t-j,i} + \sum_{j=1}^q \theta_{j,i} \epsilon_{t-j,i} \quad (2)$$

$$error_{ARIMA,i,t} = \epsilon_{i,t} - \hat{\epsilon}_{i,t} \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} error_{\hat{ARIMA},i,t} = & \beta_{0,i} \\ & + \beta_{1,i} \delta_{P_{active},i,t} \\ & + \beta_{2,i} \delta_{S_{rotor},i,t} \\ & + \beta_{3,i} \delta_{T_{nacelle},i,t} \\ & + \beta_{4,i} \delta_{S_{wind},i,t} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$error_{OLS,i,t} = error_{OLS,i,t} - error_{\hat{OLS},i,t} \quad (5)$$

drifts in signals. The CUSUM is used to analyse the evolution of the idiosyncratic component. The methodology assumes that upward trends in the idiosyncratic component are indicative for the formation of wear on a bearing and an increase in the probability that it will fail. CUSUM has however some requirements that need to be fulfilled, e.g. the data samples need to be independent and normally distributed [25]. The idiosyncratic component is however characterised by strong autocorrelation. To remove the autocorrelation, ARIMA modelling is used (Eq. 2). The ARIMA residual is subsequently used for further analysis (Eq. 3). The selection of an appropriate ARIMA model is done using the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) as a guideline. Analysis of the residual showed however that it is correlated with several support variables, e.g. P_{active} , $T_{nacelle}$, S_{wind} and S_{rotor} (see table 1). This relation is removed by regressing the ARIMA residual on these support variables (Eq. 4). The OLS residual is used for further analysis by the CUSUM (Eq. 5). The CUSUM has two parameters to set: k and H . k determines the size of the anomalies that should be detectable, H is a threshold that determines when the process is considered out-of-control. For the analysis k is set to 0.75. To identify anomalies several values for H are used: "weak evidence" for an anomaly is found if the CUSUM SH , which is a measure for the upward drift of the process, surpasses $5H$. "Mediocre evidence" is when the SH is larger than $7H$, and there is "strong evidence" if the SH is larger than $9H$. There is a positive relation between the strength of the evidence and the probability of a failure (see results). An exact quantification of this relation is the topic for future research. Because the focus of the S-pipeline is on slow-moving processes, the input data is aggregated to day-level to reduce noise.

The ML-pipeline contains multiple levels. The first level uses several machine learning models in parallel for learning the normal behaviour. Each model is a NBM on its own. As predictors the models use the following signals: the lags (1-12) of the signal of interest, the target signal that is not the signal of interest and its lags, the support signals of the turbine to which the signal of interest belongs and their lags, the target and support signals of all the other turbines in the fleet and their lags. By using the lagged values of the signals, time dependency is added to the model. By adding the signals of the other turbines in the fleet, the model becomes fleet-based. This implies that the NBM models have, depending on the size of the wind farm, several hundreds to several thousands of predictors. To handle such a high dimensionality, strong LASSO-based (L1) regularisation is used. The training of the models is done using 5-fold CV on a dataset containing four months of healthy data. The second (ensemble) level combines the predictions of the individual NBM models using Inverse Variance Weighting (Eq. 8). The variance of the errors of the NBM models is estimated using the Mean Absolute Deviation for robustness

Figure 3. Schematic overview of the ML-pipeline.

Figure 4. Schematic overview of how the data is used by the ML-pipeline.

$$MAD = \sum |x_i - \bar{x}|/n \quad (6)$$

$$std_{robust} = f_{scaling} * MAD \quad (7)$$

$$\hat{\mu} = \sum_i w_i X_i / \sum_i w_i \quad \text{with} \quad w_i = 1/\sigma_i^2 \quad (8)$$

reasons (Eq. 6, 7). For this a separate dataset containing two months of healthy data is used. Figure 4 gives an overview of how the data is divided for the training of the ensemble machine learning model. The third level detects anomalies by comparing the ensemble predictions with the observed target values. The deviations between the two are analysed using CUSUM. The parameter k is set to the value 3. A "weak evidence" alert is raised if the CUSUM SH is larger than 40. A "mediocre evidence" alert is raised if the SH surpasses 60, and a "strong evidence" alert is raised if it surpasses 100. The purpose of this model is to generate more fine-grained anomaly detections so the input data is aggregated to the hour-level. Figure 3 gives a schematic overview of the machine learning based pipeline.

4. Results

To validate the methodology, SCADA data from a large operational wind farm is used (for confidentiality reasons the results are limited to a subset of 10 turbines). The data stretches over 10 years and has a 10-minute resolution. The subset contains information on 35 generator (front/rear) bearing replacements. For the validation of the methodology it will be assumed that a replacement corresponds to a failure. This is not necessarily always the case, however it is likely to be a valid assumption for the majority of cases. Furthermore, it is probable that some replacements are missing. Small imprecisions in the time of the replacements are also possible. The validation will focus on the performance of the S- and ML-pipelines separately, how they compare to each other, what their strengths and weaknesses are and how they complement each other.

The performance of the S-pipeline is quite good. It is very capable in detecting the upward trends in the bearing temperatures that precede a bearing failure. Figure 5 shows in the green box a correct detection. The detector starts indicating that there is an issue over a year in advance. The orange box shows a suspicious event. The temperature clearly increases substantially, but there is no replacement registered during that time frame. However, from the behaviour of the temperature it can be deduced that most likely something has happened. Figure 6 shows two replacement events. Both are detected accurately well in advance. Figure 7 shows two correct detections. Also in these cases the first anomalies are raised well in advance. One might point out that identifying anomalies more than two years before the actual failure is strange. However, the wind turbine operator indicated that they had the tendency to keep

Figure 5. Detections by S-pipeline for turbine 2. Interpretation of the evidence levels: weak evidence: $CUSUM SH > CUSUM H = 5$, mediocre evidence: $CUSUM SH > CUSUM H = 7$, Strong evidence: $CUSUM SH > CUSUM H = 9$

Figure 6. Detections by S-pipeline for turbine 5. Interpretation of the evidence levels: weak evidence: $CUSUM SH > CUSUM H = 5$, mediocre evidence: $CUSUM SH > CUSUM H = 7$, Strong evidence: $CUSUM SH > CUSUM H = 9$

Figure 7. Detections by S-pipeline for turbine 10. Interpretation of the evidence levels: weak evidence: $CUSUM SH > CUSUM H = 5$, mediocre evidence: $CUSUM SH > CUSUM H = 7$, Strong evidence: $CUSUM SH > CUSUM H = 100$

turbines with damaged bearings active during a prolonged period of time without structurally solving the issue. This decision was taken due to the frequency of the occurrence of the problem and the fact that they knew its root-cause. This explains why in some cases anomalies are detected a long time before the actual bearing failure. One replacement is missed by the anomaly detector (orange box). An analysis of the temperature trend does not show any clear upward trend that might indicate a problem. However, it needs to be pointed out that this replacement happened at the same time as a replacement of the front bearing. It is possible that the rear

bearing was replaced ahead of time to avoid an extra downtime. The figures also make clear that the S-pipeline does not randomly generates anomaly warnings. The anomalies are nicely clustered in time, which is as expected.

Figure 8. Prediction of generator front bearing temperature by ML-pipeline.

Figure 9. Prediction of generator front bearing temperature by ML-pipeline. Interpretation of the evidence levels: weak evidence: $CUSUM SH > CUSUM H = 5$, mediocre evidence: $CUSUM SH > CUSUM H = 7$, Strong evidence: $CUSUM SH > CUSUM H = 100$

The ML-pipeline also performs good. A first thing to notice is the very accurate modelling of T_{front} and T_{rear} . Figure 8 shows that the machine learning ensemble is able to model the bearing temperature no matter what the operating conditions, environmental conditions, ... are (there seems to be a tendency to slightly underestimate the highest temperatures). Figure 9 shows the detections for turbine 5. Both replacements are detected. However, a comparison with the results for the S-pipeline for the same turbine shows that the detections by the ML-pipeline are much more localized. It can also be observed that the final years are, unlike for the S-pipeline, much less identified as anomalous, even though the temperature trend is clearly upwards. This is due to the fact that the ML-pipeline is a more capable modeller of the temperature signal. The S-pipeline categorizes any upward temperature trend as an anomaly, while the ML-pipeline can make a distinction between different upward trends.

Figure 10 shows the results for a turbine with a lot of generator bearing problems. All four problems were detected correctly. The detection of the second failure is however less clear. It is unclear what determines the strength of the detections. This will be investigated in future research. There is also a suspicious event to be found (first orange box). After the second replacement the temperatures kept on increasing until the beginning of year 6 when they all of a sudden decreased drastically. No information on a replacement for that time frame is available. However, it is likely that something did happen at that time. So this detection can be considered

Figure 10. Prediction of generator rear bearing temperature by ML-pipeline. Interpretation of the evidence levels: weak evidence: $CUSUM_{SH} > CUSUM_H = 5$, mediocre evidence: $CUSUM_{SH} > CUSUM_H = 7$, Strong evidence: $CUSUM_{SH} > CUSUM_H = 100$

Figure 11. Anomaly detections by ML-pipeline for turbine 2. Interpretation of the evidence levels: weak evidence: $CUSUM_{SH} > CUSUM_H = 5$, mediocre evidence: $CUSUM_{SH} > CUSUM_H = 7$, Strong evidence: $CUSUM_{SH} > CUSUM_H = 100$

Figure 12. Anomaly detections by ML-pipeline for generator rear bearing temperature for turbine 2. Interpretation of the evidence levels: weak evidence: $CUSUM_{SH} > CUSUM_H = 5$, mediocre evidence: $CUSUM_{SH} > CUSUM_H = 7$, Strong evidence: $CUSUM_{SH} > CUSUM_H = 100$

a correct detection of a suspicious event. Figure 11 shows a turbine for which no front bearing failures were detected during the observation period. It can be observed that the ML-pipeline identifies very few anomalies in the signal. This shows that the predictions by the pipeline are trustworthy, in the sense that anomalies are not generated randomly. And finally, figure 12 shows that the S-pipeline is still relevant in the whole framework. The detections by the ML-pipeline are less clear for the user than those by the S-pipeline (figure 5). This shows that

combining both pipelines in a single framework has an added value.

Table 2. Performance of the S- and ML-pipelines.

Pipeline	Accuracy	F1	Sensitivity	Specificity
S	0.74	0.74	0.71	0.77
ML	0.79	0.81	0.78	0.81

Assessing the performance of a methodology on real data is not a trivial task. Some assumptions need to be made to make it possible to identify true positives (TP), true negatives (TN), false positives (FP) and false negatives (FN). To this end a quite strict (conservative) performance assessment scheme is created. A detection is considered a TP if a substantial amount of evidence for anomalies is found during the year that precedes a failure/replacement (registered failures, not suspicious events). If during the year that follows a failure/replacement no substantial amount of evidence is found, it is classified as a TN. A FP is generated if during the year that follows a failure/replacement a substantial amount of evidence is found for anomalies, while a FN is generated if no substantial amount of evidence for anomalies is found during the year that precedes a failure/replacement. Bearing temperature signals for which no failures/replacements are known are excluded from the analysis. Table 2 gives an overview of the performance of the S- and ML-pipeline. The results show that the ML-pipeline (Accuracy score = 0.79, F1 = 0.81) outperforms the S-pipeline (Accuracy score = 0.74, F1 = 0.74). This is as expected and supports the idea that the S-pipeline is useful for a first fast scan of the data, while the ML-pipeline can do a more precise analysis. Overall the performance of both pipelines is quite good considering the validation case works with a substantial amount of real data from an operational wind farm.

5. Conclusion

The research presented here is a contribution to wind turbine predictive maintenance using SCADA data. A framework is presented that consists out of multiple complementary pipelines: a statistics-based pipeline and a machine learning-based pipeline. The statistics-based pipeline is able to do a fast, less precise, analysis of the data. It does not need a large healthy training dataset. This makes it possible to start sooner with the anomaly identification process (less waiting time). It can also be used to generate healthy training data for other, more advanced machine learning models. The machine learning-based pipeline takes more time to train, but it can make more accurate predictions and anomaly detections. The results also show that the methods are complementary. The statistics-based pipeline is less accurate, but gives on certain occasions more clear results to the user. The machine learning-based pipeline on the other hand is better able to differentiate between anomalous upward trends and normal ones. Future research will focus on using the statistics pipeline as a way to extract healthy training data for the machine learning-based pipeline. Other ensemble methods and NBM models will also be investigated.

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